

Spin-polarized quantum transport in laterally connected zigzag-triangular graphene nanodots

Hazem Abdelsalam^{1,2*}, Omar H. Abd-Elkader³, Mahmoud A. S. Sakr⁴, Nahed H. Teleb^{1,5},
Vasil A. Saroka^{6,7,8}, Qinfang Zhang^{1*}

¹School of Materials Science and Engineering, Yancheng Institute of Technology, Yancheng
224051, PR China

²Theoretical Physics Department, National Research Centre, El-Buhouth Str., 12622, Dokki,
Giza, Egypt

³Department of Physics and Astronomy, College of Science, King Saud University, P.O. Box
2455, Riyadh 11451, Saudi Arabia

⁴Center of Basic Science (CBS), Misr University for Science and Technology (MUST), 6th
October City, Egypt

⁵Electron Microscope and Thin Films Department, National Research Centre, El-Buhouth Str.,
12622, Dokki, Giza, Egypt

⁶Department of Physics, University of Rome Tor Vergata and INFN, Via della Ricerca
Scientifica 1, 00133, Roma, Italy

⁷Institute for Nuclear Problems, Belarusian State University, Bobruiskaya 11, 220030, Minsk,
Belarus

⁸TBpack Ltd., 27 Old Gloucester Street, London WC1N 3AX, UK

Corresponding Authors: hazemabdelhameed@gmail.com (Hazem Abdelsalam),
qfangzhang@gmail.com (Qinfang Zhang).

Abstract

Spintronic devices with enhanced spin quantum transport are crucial for future computing technology. Here we investigate the magnetic, electro-optical, and transport properties of 2D chains from laterally connected zigzag triangular graphene (ZTG) nanodots using first principle calculations. The optimized structures show that ZTG connected with an even number of C-atoms have a planer structure while those linked with odd numbers experience noticeable twisting. The twisting can be removed by considering the effect of the substrate due to van der Waals interactions with the substrate. Vibrational frequencies and binding energies confirmed the structural stability of the considered ZTG chains. The ZTG chains have ferromagnetic spin ordering proportional to the number of linked ZTG that can even increase in odd-linked chains due to the unpaired electrons from the odd link. For instance, 3ZTG coupled by an even link (2C) is a ferromagnetic chain coupled by a nonmagnetic link while odd linking (3C) results in a ferromagnetic chain with higher net spin and ferromagnetic coupling. The I-V curves indicate that the current in the latter chain is significantly higher than that in the former, especially for the spin-up current. Moreover, its transmission spectra reveal only one sharp spin-up peak within the bias window at an applied voltage of 1.5 V. Therefore, the considered ZTG chains with odd links are promising spin filters for spintronic applications.

Keywords: linked Zigzag-triangular graphene; DFT and nonequilibrium Green's functions; spintronics; quantum transport; spin filter.

1. Introduction

Spintronics is a perspective technology that uses quantum spin property for information storage, processing, and communication[1-3]. When compared to conventional electronics, it offers such advantages as energy efficiency, non-volatility, fast operation, and read-out. These properties can change the architecture of modern computers by eliminating the difference between dynamical volatile and long-term non-volatile memories. Unlike a similar field of quantum computing[4] the one that is based on solid-state spin qubits [5-9], spintronic does not necessarily require keeping coherence of the entangled quantum spin states. In contrast, it can be satisfied with only thermodynamic averages. This latter fact makes spintronics more accessible and attractive for immediate application. The search for novel technologically relevant and compatible materials, however, is still ongoing.

Many materials have been proposed as good candidates for spintronics applications. Ferromagnets and antiferromagnets both metallic and insulating ones are the most obvious candidates. Metallic ferromagnets (Heusler compounds[10], manganese perovskites[11]), insulating ferromagnets (CrI₃ and Cr₂S₃[12], insulating antiferromagnets (transition metal oxides such as MnO, NiO, FeO, CoO[13,14] and halides such as MnF₂[15,16] and FeF₂[17] exhibiting easy-axis and easy-plane anisotropies, respectively)[18] metallic antiferromagnets (CuMnAs, Mn₃Sn, Mn₂Au, and FeRh)[19], semiconducting antiferromagnets (MnTe[20] and CuFeS₂[21]) – all exhibit a range of interesting magnonic and spin wave phenomena. Ferromagnetic materials are easily controlled but they produce stray magnetic fields, and they are very sensitive to external perturbations. Antiferromagnetic materials are robust with respect to magnetic perturbation but more difficult to manipulate, but they make possible more compact spintronic devices. Magnetic insulators are promising for reducing heat losses in spintronic devices due to chargeless spin transport, while metallic magnetic materials provide convenient spin-to-charge conversion and electrical read-out. Thus, transport phenomena are of particular importance for the field of spintronics. Despite the Mermin-Wagner theorem that advocates the absence of ferro- and antiferromagnetism in one- and two-dimensions[22], 2D monolayer and thin film materials CrI₃[23,24], LaCoO₃[25] V₂Se₂O[26] and FeCl₂[27] have emerged as a new fruitful playground for spintronic applications.

All the above-mentioned classical magnetic materials share their multielement compound nature. Single-element carbon materials stand out from this vast and diverse background and occupy a special place in the list of magnetic materials for spintronic applications. For a long time, the field of organic carbon magnetism has remained elusive and even controversial. Graphene nanoribbons[28-40], modified graphene edges[41-52], and nanographenes[53-65] were predicted to host edge localized states providing a large density of states at the Fermi energy which in accordance with Stoner's criterion[66,67] promises ferromagnetism. Once became feasible and accurate enough, the experiments started confirming these theoretical predictions[68-72]

Recently, the family of organic materials has been joined by two new members. Triangulene[73-79] and Clar's goblet[80] have arisen on the horizon as experimentally accessible nanostructures. Both these elements have theoretically shown great potential for spintronic applications, including digital logic[61,81-99]. Not only have atomically precise syntheses of large triangulenes been achieved (4-, 5- and 7-triangulenes[74,76,100] but also a controlled covalent bonding between such nanostructures has been demonstrated by producing dimers[75] and chains of triangulene[101] This opens a venue for investigating previous theoretical predictions such as topological corner states[102] or electric field manipulation of magnetic order[99]. Concurrently, even more complicated structures such as triangulene-based covalent organic frameworks[103] can be envisaged and proposed. Nevertheless, an important question of how magnetic states of such spintronic building blocks can be efficiently read out persists and awaits a definite answer.

In this work, we study the best ways of assembling the triangulene-based spintronic elements into proto-circuits by preserving their unique properties and possibly revealing emerging new ones. Namely, we investigate how the electronic and magnetic properties alter if two or three triangulene elements (triangular graphene nanodots) are laterally connected via carbon chains – carbynes – and if/how triangulene spin-states could be read out via spin-sensitive transport measurements.

2. Computational Model

The magnetic, electronic, and quantum transport properties of the laterally connected triangular graphene nanodots are explored using density functional theory calculations as executed in Gaussian 16 software[104]. The level of theory considered for the calculations is the B3LYP/6-31g [105-107] which shows good results on C-based (and similar atomic size) 2D materials when considering both accuracy and computational time [108-110]. Grimme's dispersion correction (gd3) is added to the B3LYP functional to account for the van der Waals interactions that exist between the connected triangular nanodots [111]. The obtained output files from Gaussian 16 are further processed in Multiwfn to calculate the partial density of states [112]. Time-dependent DFT calculations (TD-DFT) for the first 50 excited states are performed to study the UV-vis absorption spectra and related optical properties such as oscillator strength and transition composition. The quantum transport properties are simulated based on the nonequilibrium Green's function (NEGF) within the Keldysh formalism in combination with DFT (NEGF-DFT) as implemented in Nanocal [113,114]. The exchange-correlation function is described by the local density approximation (LDA) and the cutoff energy is set to 80 Hartree. In our investigation, we didn't consider the Coulomb blockade effect which is expected to be not effective here due to the negligible tunnel barriers between ZTG and the electrodes similar to previous work on C60 [114]. In the case of connected 2ZTG, the K points for the electrode were set to (1,1,100) points and (1,1,10) points for the Brillouin zone in the self-consistent computation. In the case of linked 3ZTG, the K points for the electrode were set to (3,1,100) points and (3,1,10) points for the Brillouin zone in the self-consistent computation.

3. Results and Discussions

The considered nanosystems are shown in Fig. 1 where zigzag-triangular graphene (ZTG) nanoflakes or triangulenes are connected by an even number of C-atoms (2C as an example) and odd number (3C atoms). The resultant system from connecting two ZTG by 2C/3C atoms is shown in Fig. 1 (a)/(b). We consider also the linking of three ZTG by 2C and 3C as seen in Fig. 1 (c,d). It is noted in the optimized structures in Fig. 1 that linking with 3C atoms causes twisting of the ZTG with respect to each other. In the case of linking with 2C-atoms, they form an in-plane triple bond between each other and single bonds with ZTG. This strong triple bond prevents the twisting of the ZTG nanodots. When linking with 3C atoms the middle C atom of the link forms two double bonds while the other 2C atoms form weaker bonds with the ZTG nanodots. These weaker bonds and the longer size of the link in the case of linking with 3C atoms are the reason for the observed twisting. The longer size of the link in the case of 3C is not the reason for the twisting because the optimized structure of ZTG connected with a longer link consisting of 4C atoms, see Fig. S1(a), is planar similar to the case of 2ZTG-2C. Moreover, the electronic and magnetic properties that will be discussed later are similar in both cases of linking with 2C (Fig. 2, 3) and 4C (Fig. S1 b-f). Thus linking ZTG with 2C atoms can be used as a representative example of linking with an even number of C-atoms and 3C represents odd linking.

Fig. 1. The optimized structures of laterally connected ZTG by 2C and 3C atoms for two ZTG (a,b) and three ZTG (c,d).

The twisting, by increasing the number of linking C atoms, is observed only in the free-standing case. However, by considering the substrate on which these nanosystems could be grown, the structures become planar as seen in Fig. S1 (g) for 2ZTRG-3C supported by hBN substrate. Since the interactions between the connected ZTG and the substrate are only by van der Waals forces,

the magnetic properties and electronic properties are almost the same as the free-standing cases. For example, the spin density and the highest occupied/lowest unoccupied (HOMO/LUMO) distributions of the free-standing 2ZTRG-3C (see Figs. 2,3) and the substrate supported one (in Fig. S1 h-l). Thus we consider only the four free-standing cases in the following sections.

3.1 Optimized Molecular Structures

The structural parameters like bond length (Å), dihedral, and bond angles (degrees) of the four free-standing structures are summarized in Table 1. It is observed that ZTG-based compounds exhibit interesting structural characteristics. The most notable finding was that the ZTG unit in all studied compounds is fully planar. The dihedral angles C1-C2-C3-C6 and C5-C4-C3-C6, which are important indicators of planarity, fall within 179.99° and 180.00° for all ZTG-based materials, including 2ZTG-2C, 3ZTG-2C, 2ZTG-3C, and 3ZTG-3C. Among the derivatives, 2ZTG-3C and 3ZTG-3C (Figure 1) demonstrate rotations of each ZTG unit by an angle of 90° compared to 2ZTG-2C and 3ZTG-2C (Figure 1). This observation is attributed to the higher number of carbon atoms (odd number) in the bridge between ZTG units. The bond angles C1-C2-C3 and C8-C9-C10 in all studied structures were approximately 121.00°, indicating sp² hybridization of hexagonal groups within these molecular chains. Furthermore, the lengths of the C1-C2, C3-C6, and C8-C9 bonds show an interesting trend. They are not affected by the number of ZTG units or the number of carbon atoms in the bridge between ZTG units (Table 1). In summary, the investigation of ZTG derivatives provides valuable insights into their structural characteristics, particularly their planarity, dihedral angles, and bond lengths.

Table 1 Some important quantum parameters like bond length (Å), dihedral, and bond angles (degrees) for 2ZTG-2C, 2ZTG-3C, 3ZTG-2C, and 3ZTG-3C.

Designation	2ZTG-2C	3ZTG-2C	2ZTG-3C	3ZTG-3C
C1-C2	1.42	1.42	1.42	1.42
C3-C6	1.43	1.43	1.40	1.40
C8-C9	1.41	1.41	1.42	1.42
C1-C2-C3	121.31	121.32	121.52	121.52
C8-C9-C10	121.31	121.33	121.52	121.48
C1-C2-C3-C6	179.99	180.00	180.00	180.00
C5-C4-C3-C6	179.99	179.99	180.00	180.00

3.2 Molecular Structure Stability

In our study assessing the stability of ZTG derivatives, a crucial parameter investigated was the binding energy (BE), determined by the equation $BE = (N_C E_C + N_H E_H - E_t) / N_t$. Here, N_C , N_H , and N_t represent the numbers of carbon, hydrogen, and total atoms, while E_C , E_H , and E_t correspond to the total energies of carbon atoms, hydrogen atoms, and the final compound, respectively. Analysis

of the calculated binding energies yielded positive values ranging from 7.268 to 7.332 eV, signifying the stable formation of ZTG derivative compounds. Specifically, for 2ZTG-2C, 3ZTG-2C, 2ZTG-3C, and 3ZTG-3C, the obtained binding energies were 7.272, 7.332, 7.268, and 7.326 eV, respectively. Among the investigated molecular structures, 3ZTG-2C exhibited the highest stability, while 2ZTG-2C displayed the lowest stability. This confirms the stable formation of ZTG derivatives, and our findings highlight that the 3ZTG-2C configuration emerges as the most stable among the examined molecular structures. In summary, our investigation into binding energies provides valuable insights into the stability and characteristics of ZTG derivatives.

In addition to binding energy, we performed frequency calculations to obtain the vibrational frequency from which the dynamical stability can be tested. From the infrared spectra shown in Fig. S1 of Appendix A, it is clear that all the vibrational frequencies are real (positive) which indicates that the optimized structures correspond to a minimum on the potential energy surface and the structure is dynamically stable.

3.3 Magnetic properties

The magnetic calculations, namely spin-polarized and nonpolarized calculations, show that all the considered structures have ferromagnetic spin ordering with non-zero net spin (S). The ferromagnetic spin nonet state with $S=4$ is found to be the magnetic state having the lowest ground state energy of 2ZTG-2C. This net spin is just the sum of the individual ZTG which is a result of the imbalance between the number of C-atoms in the sublattices A and B according to Lieb's theorem[115]. The values of the net spin are shown in the spin density distribution for the considered structures in Fig. 2. For 2ZTG-3C, the net spin increases to $S=5$ where the additional unpaired two electrons come from the left and right C-atoms of the link. The origin of spin enhancement can be seen also in the spin density distribution in Fig. 2 (b) where two considerable spin-up cubes (blue) are localized on the left and right atoms of the link. These two cubes are not observed in 2ZTG-2C in Fig. 2 (a) and the spin-up cubes distribute only on the two ZTG.

Fig. 2. Spin density distributions of spin up (blue) and spin down (red) orbitals of the laterally connected two (a,b) and three ZTG (c,d) nanodots.

Connecting three ZTG by 2C/3C (Fig. 2 c, d) atoms increases the net spin to 6/8 due to the same reason of enhancement discussed in connected two ZTG. It is noted from the spin density distributions in Fig. 2 (a, c) that the nonmagnetic 2C atoms connecting the ZTG have spin-down distribution on them that come from the spin-down electrons on the apex of the ZTG. On the other hand, the 3C atoms connecting two and three ZTG in Fig. 2 (b,d) have spin distribution dominated by spin-up charges.

3.4 Electronic Properties

After identifying the right spin state of the structures, we can proceed to investigate their electronic properties. The partial density of states with the spin-up and spin-down energy gaps included in Fig. 3 indicates that the connected ZTG nanodots are semiconductors with link-dependent energy gaps. First let us indicate that the blue density peaks in Fig. 3 (a,b) represent not only peaks from the second ZTG (G2) as shown in the plots but also the first ZTG (G1) peaks because G1 and G2 peaks overlap and only G2 appears in the plots. In the case of 3ZTG, G1 and G2 peaks overlap and only G2 peaks are seen but the peaks of the middle ZTG (G2) are different from them and can be seen separately.

Fig. 3. The partial density of states (a-d) and the corresponding HOMO and LUMO distributions (e-h) of the linked ZTG.

It is clearly seen from Fig. 3 (a,b) that both the spin up and down energy gaps increase from $E_{g\alpha}/E_{g\beta} = 2.8/2.91$ eV to $3.41/3.35$ eV by increasing the linking atoms from two to three C atoms. The triple bond in the link of 2C connected 2ZTG-2C or 3ZTG-2C structures is the reason for the lower band gap where one of the π -bonds forms molecular orbitals with low energy that corresponds to the low energy gap. These orbitals appear as the low red density peaks in Fig. 3 (a,c). On the other hand, they do not appear in ZTG connected with three C atoms (Fig. 3 b,d) and consequently, the energy gap gets larger. By comparing the HOMO and LUMO in Fig. 3 (e,f), we found also that a considerable part of the HOMO and LUMO distribute on the linking atoms in the case of 2ZTG-

2C while no distribution on the link in 2ZTG-3C. The same is also found in the HOMO and LUMO distributions of 3ZTG-2C and 3ZTG-3C in Fig. 3 (g,h).

3.5 Quantum chemical parameters

The quantum chemical parameters (QCP) parameters, including dipole moment (μ), chemical potential (ρ), electronegativity (χ), and chemical hardness (η) were calculated for spin-up electrons using the HOMO energy (E_H) and the LUMO energy (E_L). These parameters were determined using the following equations: $\rho = \frac{E_H + E_L}{2}$, $\chi = -\frac{E_H + E_L}{2}$, and $\eta = \frac{E_L - E_H}{2}$ [116]. Table 2 presents the quantum chemical parameters (QCC) for the examined molecular structures. Notably, 3ZTG-3C stands out with the highest dipole moment (μ), indicative of an asymmetry in its spin-up electronic charge distribution. This observation implies that 3ZTG-3C undergoes more active intramolecular charge transfer compared to the other structures. 3ZTG-2C demonstrates the most negative chemical potential (ρ), suggesting a higher likelihood for spin-up electrons to escape. Furthermore, the elevated electronegativity values for 3ZTG-2C underscore its strong electron-attracting characteristics. In terms of chemical hardness (η), a measure of resistance to charge transfer, 2ZTG-3C exhibits the highest value, indicating its greater resistance to charge transfer compared to other structures. In contrast, 3ZTG-2C displays the lowest hardness value, implying a lower resistance to charge transfer. These findings shed light on the diverse electronic properties of the examined structures, providing valuable insights into their charge transfer tendencies and electron distribution characteristics.

Table 2. The HOMO energy (E_H), the LUMO energy (E_L), chemical potential (ρ), electronegativity (χ), chemical hardness (η), and dipole moment (μ), for spin-up of selected ZTG-based materials.

compounds	H (eV)	L(eV)	ρ (eV)	χ (eV)	η (eV)	μ (D)
2ZTG-2C	-4.490	-1.687	-3.089	3.089	1.402	0.000163
3ZTG-2C	-4.496	-1.708	-3.102	3.102	1.394	0.102888
2ZTG-3C	-4.514	-1.125	-2.820	2.820	1.695	0.000178
3ZTG-3C	-4.518	-1.159	-2.839	2.839	1.680	0.211636

3.6 Optical investigations

In this section, an examination of the UV-Vis absorption spectra for ZTG finite chains is undertaken. The resultant spectra are thoughtfully depicted in Fig. 4, with corresponding parameters thoughtfully summarized in Table 3. Our principal focus was on scrutinizing the impact of augmenting the number of ZTG units and the number of carbon atoms within the bridge linking these units on the UV-Vis absorption spectra. These absorption spectra are intricately linked to the electronic properties of the materials, arising from electronic transitions between occupied and unoccupied molecular orbitals (MOs). Consequently, alterations in the optical absorption peaks are anticipated to correlate with the electronic modifications induced by varying ZTG unit

numbers. Our investigation has unveiled a noteworthy influence on the absorption spectra of the ZTG compounds through an increase in the number of ZTG units and carbon atoms in the interconnecting bridge, manifesting as a discernible redshift, as visually elucidated in Fig. 4. In particular, 3ZTG-2C's absorption spectra indicate a redshift in comparison to other structures. The respective λ_{\max} values for 2ZTG-2C, 2ZTG-3C, 3ZTG-2C, and 3ZTG-3C are 410.22 nm, 404.28 nm, 488.68 nm, and 404.46 nm, corresponding to H \rightarrow L+5, H \rightarrow L+2, H-1 \rightarrow L+1, and H \rightarrow L+1 transitions. In conclusion, our systematic investigation of the UV-Vis absorption spectra of diverse ZTG derivatives underscores the pronounced impact of increasing ZTG unit numbers on the optical properties of ZTG-based compounds. The observed redshifts and delineated transitions provide insightful revelations into the electronic structure and behavior of materials rooted in ZTG.

Fig. 4. The UV-Vis absorption spectra of ZTG-based materials.

Table 3 The calculated excited state (ES), maximum wavelength (λ_{\max}), transition energy (TE), electronic transition (ET), oscillator strength (f), and transition coefficient (TC) for ZTG-based materials.

compounds	ES	λ_{\max} (nm)	TE (eV)	ET	f	TC
2ZTG-2C	37	410.22	3.022	H \rightarrow L+5	0.35	0.4245
3ZTG-2C	18	488.68	2.537	H \rightarrow L+2	0.16	0.9992
2ZTG-3C	25	404.28	3.067	H \rightarrow L+1	0.06	0.2465
3ZTG-3C	37	405.01	3.065	H-1 \rightarrow L+1	2.16	0.9945

3.7. Quantum transport properties

To have an insight into the quantum transport through these connected nanodots and the effect of links, we calculate the I-V curves and transmission of these devices. Fig. 1 shows the schematic diagram for the devices constructed to calculate the quantum transport properties.

Fig. 5. Schematic diagrams of the constructed devices from two and three connected ZTG nanodots. Where S is the source, the middle is the active scattering region and D is the Drain.

The source (S) and drain (d) in cases of two connected ZTG are armchair nanoribbons that are doped with few N atoms to increase the conductivity. In the case of three ZTG, the source and drain are zigzag nanoribbons which are conductors, and then no doping is considered. The case of 3ZTG-3C with source and drain doped with N atoms was tested and the current values are even lower than without doping. The current values of two ZTG connected without any linking C-atoms in Fig. 6 (a) show that the current values are higher than that after linking with even or odd C atoms. For example, at an applied bias of 1.5 V, the spin up/down current in 2ZTG is 0.10/0.44 (μA) while in 2ZTG-3C the spin up/down current significantly decreases to 0.7/4.6 (nA). The same is observed in 3ZTG-2C with even lower currents. In contrast, 3ZTG-3C has a higher spin-up current of 0.02 (μA) which could be a result of the contribution of the links to the spin-up electrons as discussed before. Increasing the bias voltage to 3 V decreases the difference in current between connected ZTG with and without links. Even though, spin up and down currents of 2ZTG are still higher by at least one order of magnitude. Therefore, it is a trade of process, to enhance the ferromagnetism we need to accept the decrease of the transport current. This decrease can be minimized by considering an odd number of linking atoms and three or more linked ZTG such as 3ZTG-3C.

Fig. 6. The I-V curves of the connected 2ZTG (a), 2ZTG-3C (b), 3ZTG-2C (c), 3ZTG-3C (d). (e-g) The transmission spectra of the considered five structures in (a-d) at different bias voltages, the black vertical lines represent the bias window.

The transmission spectra shown in Fig. 6 (e), (f), (g), and (h) for 2ZTG, 2ZTG-3C, 3ZTG-2C, and 3ZTG-3C respectively, also give useful information regarding the transport through these nanodevices. Using the same example, at a bias voltage of 1.5 V, it is observed in the transition spectra of 2ZTG that only one spin-down peak enters the bias window. The magnitude of the current is the integral area of this bias window that can be seen as the higher spin-down current in Fig. 6 (a). At 1.5 V, no transmission peaks enter the bias window in the cases of 2ZTG-3C and 3ZTG-2C. By further increasing the voltage to 2.5, both spin-up and spin-down transmission peaks enter the window in the case of 2ZTG and 2ZTG-3C (see Fig. 6 e, f). On the other hand, no peaks appear in 3ZTG-2C even at this high bias voltage which agrees with the negligible current ($\leq 10^{-10}$ A) in Fig. 6 (c). Interestingly, 3ZTG-3C has only one considerable spin-up peak inside the bias window at 1.5 V. This peak, which confirms the noticeable spin-up current in 3ZTG-3C (Fig. 6 d), indicates that this device can be used as an efficient spin filter at given bias voltage.

Conclusion

The electronic, magnetic, optical, and quantum transport properties of zigzag-triangular graphene (ZTG) nanodots that are laterally connected by odd and even numbers of C-atoms are investigated using DFT calculations. In the free-standing case, two ZTG or three ZTG connected by 2C or in general even numbers of C atoms have a planer structure while those connected with odd numbers experience twisting of one layer with respect to the other. This twisting disappears if we consider the substrate effect where the van der Waals interactions between the substrate and the connected ZTG prevent twisting. The vibrational frequencies and the binding energies calculations confirm the dynamical stability of considered nanosystems. It is known that the direct linking of ZTG forms a nanographene chain with antiferromagnetic spin ordering ($S=0$). Here we show that the ferromagnetic spin ordering of isolated ZTG can be maintained and even increased by connecting ZTG with even and odd C-atoms, respectively. For instance, the considered ZTG has $S=2$ that summed up to $S=4$ in 2ZTG connected by 2C atoms or $S=5$ when connected by 3C. The link in the first case (2C) has no unpaired electrons and does not add to the ferromagnetism while 3C has two unpaired electrons that increase the net spin to $S=5$. The electronic properties show that the finite ZTG chains connected with 2C have lower spin up/down energy gaps ($\sim 2.8/2.9$ eV) compared to those of odd-connected chains (3.4/3.3 eV). The triple bond in the 2C link provides a π -bond that forms molecular orbitals with low energy which are responsible for the decrease of the energy gap as confirmed by the low energy gaps in the partial density of states distribution and the distribution of the HOMO/LUMO. Quantum transport investigations indicate that the current through directly connected ZTG is higher than the current after linking, especially in cases with links consisting of even C-atoms. However, increasing the number of unpaired electrons, from the links such as in 3ZTG connected by two odd links, leads to a significant increase in the current. Interestingly, the spin-up current in this chain is significantly higher than the spin-down one. Additionally, its transmission spectra show only one sharp spin-up peak inside the bias window.

Therefore, ZTG chains linked with odd C-atoms can be employed as spin filters in spintronic applications.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, H.A.; methodology, H.A. and Q.Z.; software, Q.Z.; validation, H.A.; formal analysis, O.H.A.-E.; investigation, H.A. and V.A.S.; resources, O.H.A.-E.; data curation, H.A. and V.A.S; writing—original draft preparation, O.H.A.-E., M.A., N.T, V.A.S. and H.A.; writing—review and editing, O.H.A.-E., N.T., and Q.Z.; visualization, O.H.A.-E., N.T., and M.A.; supervision, O.H.A.-E. and Q.Z.; project administration, O.H.A.-E. and H.A.; funding acquisition, O.H.A.-E. and Q.Z. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 12274361), the Natural Science Foundation of Jiangsu Province (BK20211361), and College Natural Science Research Project of Jiangsu Province (20KJA430004). V. A. S. was partly supported by EU HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01 (project no. 101065500, TeraExc). This work is supported also by Researchers Supporting Project number (RSP2024R468), King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. H. Abdelsalam thanks Xiaowen Shi (from HZWTECH) for her help and discussions regarding this study.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding authors.

Acknowledgments: This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 12274361), the Natural Science Foundation of Jiangsu Province (BK20211361), and College Natural Science Research Project of Jiangsu Province (20KJA430004). V. A. S. was partly supported by EU HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01 (project no. 101065500, TeraExc). This work is supported also by Researchers Supporting Project number (RSP2024R468), King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. H. Abdelsalam thanks Xiaowen Shi (from HZWTECH) for her help and discussions regarding this study.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Žutić, I.; Fabian, J.; Das Sarma, S. Spintronics: Fundamentals and applications. *Reviews of Modern Physics* **2004**, *76*, 323-410, doi:10.1103/RevModPhys.76.323.
2. Hirohata, A.; Yamada, K.; Nakatani, Y.; Prejbeanu, I.-L.; Diény, B.; Pirro, P.; Hillebrands, B. Review on spintronics: Principles and device applications. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* **2020**, *509*, 166711, doi:10.1016/j.jmmm.2020.166711.
3. Rajput, P.J.; Bhandari, S.U.; Wadhwa, G. A Review on—Spintronics an Emerging Technology. *Silicon* **2022**, *14*, 9195-9210, doi:10.1007/s12633-021-01643-x.
4. DiVincenzo, D.P. The Physical Implementation of Quantum Computation. 2000, 2000; pp. 771-783.

5. Kouwenhoven, L.P.; Austing, D.G.; Tarucha, S. Few-electron quantum dots. *Reports on Progress in Physics* **2001**, *64*, 701-736, doi:10.1088/0034-4885/64/6/201.
6. Hanson, R.; Kouwenhoven, L.P.; Petta, J.R.; Tarucha, S.; Vandersypen, L.M.K. Spins in few-electron quantum dots. *Reviews of Modern Physics* **2007**, *79*, 1217-1265, doi:10.1103/RevModPhys.79.1217.
7. Kloeffel, C.; Loss, D. Prospects for Spin-Based Quantum Computing in Quantum Dots. *Annual Review of Condensed Matter Physics* **2013**, *4*, 51-81, doi:10.1146/annurev-conmatphys-030212-184248.
8. Russ, M.; Burkard, G. Three-electron spin qubits. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* **2017**, *29*, 393001, doi:10.1088/1361-648X/aa761f.
9. Burkard, G.; Ladd, T.D.; Pan, A.; Nichol, J.M.; Petta, J.R. Semiconductor spin qubits. *Reviews of Modern Physics* **2023**, *95*, 025003, doi:10.1103/RevModPhys.95.025003.
10. De Groot, R.A.; Mueller, F.M.; Engen, P.G.V.; Buschow, K.H.J. New Class of Materials: Half-Metallic Ferromagnets. *Physical Review Letters* **1983**, *50*, 2024-2027, doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.50.2024.
11. Park, J.-H.; Vescovo, E.; Kim, H.-J.; Kwon, C.; Ramesh, R.; Venkatesan, T. Direct evidence for a half-metallic ferromagnet. *Nature* **1998**, *392*, 794-796, doi:10.1038/33883.
12. Li, P.; Xu, C.; Luo, W. Layer-independent ferromagnetic insulators in a new structural phase of Cr₂S₃. *Physical Review Materials* **2022**, *6*, 054006, doi:10.1103/PhysRevMaterials.6.054006.
13. Roth, W.L. Magnetic Structures of MnO, FeO, CoO, and NiO. *Physical Review* **1958**, *110*, 1333-1341, doi:10.1103/PhysRev.110.1333.
14. Hutchings, M.T.; Samuelsen, E.J. Measurement of Spin-Wave Dispersion in NiO by Inelastic Neutron Scattering and Its Relation to Magnetic Properties. *Physical Review B* **1972**, *6*, 3447-3461, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.6.3447.
15. Jacobs, I.S. Spin-Flopping in MnF₂ by High Magnetic Fields. *Journal of Applied Physics* **1961**, *32*, S61-S62, doi:10.1063/1.2000500.
16. Higuchi, T.; Kuwata-Gonokami, M. Control of antiferromagnetic domain distribution via polarization-dependent optical annealing. *Nature Communications* **2016**, *7*, 10720, doi:10.1038/ncomms10720.
17. Strempler, J.; Rütt, U.; Bayrakci, S.P.; Brückel, T.; Jauch, W. Magnetic properties of transition metal fluorides M F₂ (M = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni) via high-energy photon diffraction. *Physical Review B* **2004**, *69*, 014417, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.69.014417.
18. Rezende, S.M.; Azevedo, A.; Rodríguez-Suárez, R.L. Introduction to antiferromagnetic magnons. *Journal of Applied Physics* **2019**, *126*, 151101, doi:10.1063/1.5109132.
19. Siddiqui, S.A.; Sklenar, J.; Kang, K.; Gilbert, M.J.; Schleife, A.; Mason, N.; Hoffmann, A. Metallic antiferromagnets. *Journal of Applied Physics* **2020**, *128*, 040904, doi:10.1063/5.0009445.
20. Kriegner, D.; Výborný, K.; Olejník, K.; Reichlová, H.; Novák, V.; Marti, X.; Gazquez, J.; Saidl, V.; Němec, P.; Volobuev, V.V.; et al. Multiple-stable anisotropic magnetoresistance memory in antiferromagnetic MnTe. *Nature Communications* **2016**, *7*, 11623, doi:10.1038/ncomms11623.
21. Takaki, H.; Kobayashi, K.; Shimono, M.; Kobayashi, N.; Hirose, K.; Tsujii, N.; Mori, T. First-principles calculations of Seebeck coefficients in a magnetic semiconductor CuFeS₂. *Applied Physics Letters* **2017**, *110*, 072107, doi:10.1063/1.4976574.
22. Mermin, N.D.; Wagner, H. Absence of Ferromagnetism or Antiferromagnetism in One- or Two-Dimensional Isotropic Heisenberg Models. *Physical Review Letters* **1966**, *17*, 1133-1136, doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.17.1133.
23. Niu, B.; Su, T.; Francisco, B.A.; Ghosh, S.; Kargar, F.; Huang, X.; Lohmann, M.; Li, J.; Xu, Y.; Taniguchi, T.; et al. Coexistence of Magnetic Orders in Two-Dimensional Magnet CrI₃. *Nano Letters* **2020**, *20*, 553-558, doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.9b04282.

24. Zhang, P.; Chung, T.-F.; Li, Q.; Wang, S.; Wang, Q.; Huey, W.L.B.; Yang, S.; Goldberger, J.E.; Yao, J.; Zhang, X. All-optical switching of magnetization in atomically thin CrI₃. *Nature Materials* **2022**, doi:10.1038/s41563-022-01354-7.
25. Li, D.; Wang, H.; Li, K.; Zhu, B.; Jiang, K.; Backes, D.; Veiga, L.S.I.; Shi, J.; Roy, P.; Xiao, M.; et al. Emergent and robust ferromagnetic-insulating state in highly strained ferroelastic LaCoO₃ thin films. *Nature Communications* **2023**, *14*, 3638, doi:10.1038/s41467-023-39369-6.
26. Ma, H.-Y.; Hu, M.; Li, N.; Liu, J.; Yao, W.; Jia, J.-F.; Liu, J. Multifunctional antiferromagnetic materials with giant piezomagnetism and noncollinear spin current. *Nature Communications* **2021**, *12*, 2846, doi:10.1038/s41467-021-23127-7.
27. Zhou, X.; Brzostowski, B.; Durajski, A.; Liu, M.; Xiang, J.; Jiang, T.; Wang, Z.; Chen, S.; Li, P.; Zhong, Z.; et al. Atomically Thin 1T-FeCl₂ Grown by Molecular-Beam Epitaxy. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2020**, *124*, 9416-9423, doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.0c03050.
28. Fujita, M.; Wakabayashi, K.; Nakada, K.; Kusakabe, K. Peculiar Localized State at Zigzag Graphite Edge. *Journal of the Physics Society Japan* **1996**, *65*, 1920-1923, doi:10.1143/JPSJ.65.1920.
29. Nakada, K.; Fujita, M.; Dresselhaus, G.; Dresselhaus, M.S. Edge state in graphene ribbons: Nanometer size effect and edge shape dependence. *Physical Review B* **1996**, *54*, 17954-17961, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.54.17954.
30. Wakabayashi, K.; Fujita, M.; Ajiki, H.; Sigrist, M. Electronic and magnetic properties of nanographite ribbons. *Physical Review B* **1999**, *59*, 8271-8282, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.59.8271.
31. Miyamoto, Y.; Nakada, K.; Fujita, M. First-principles study of edge states of H-terminated graphitic ribbons. *Physical Review B* **1999**, *59*, 9858-9861, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.59.9858.
32. Kusakabe, K.; Maruyama, M. Magnetic nanographite. *Physical Review B* **2003**, *67*, 092406, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.67.092406.
33. Son, Y.-W.; Cohen, M.L.; Louie, S.G. Half-metallic graphene nanoribbons. *Nature* **2006**, *444*, 347-349, doi:10.1038/nature05180.
34. Kan, E.-J.; Li, Z.; Yang, J.; Hou, J.G. Will zigzag graphene nanoribbon turn to half metal under electric field? *Applied Physics Letters* **2007**, *91*, 243116, doi:10.1063/1.2821112.
35. Sawada, K.; Ishii, F.; Saito, M. Band-Gap Tuning in Magnetic Graphene Nanoribbons. *Applied Physics Express* **2008**, *1*, 064004, doi:10.1143/APEX.1.064004.
36. Yazyev, O.V. Emergence of magnetism in graphene materials and nanostructures. *Reports on Progress in Physics* **2010**, *73*, 056501, doi:10.1088/0034-4885/73/5/056501.
37. Wakabayashi, K.; Sasaki, K.-I.; Nakanishi, T.; Enoki, T. Electronic states of graphene nanoribbons and analytical solutions. *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials* **2010**, *11*, 054504, doi:10.1088/1468-6996/11/5/054504.
38. Wakabayashi, K.; Dutta, S. Nanoscale and edge effect on electronic properties of graphene. *Solid State Communications* **2012**, *152*, 1420-1430, doi:10.1016/j.ssc.2012.04.025.
39. Boukhvalov, D.W.; Moehlecke, S.; da Silva, R.R.; Kopelevich, Y. Effect of oxygen adsorption on magnetic properties of graphite. *Physical Review B* **2011**, *83*, 233408, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.83.233408.
40. Liu, H.; Hu, B.; Liu, N. The opposite induced magnetic moment in narrow zigzag graphene nanoribbons. *Physics Letters, Section A: General, Atomic and Solid State Physics* **2016**, *380*, 3738-3742, doi:10.1016/j.physleta.2016.09.012.
41. Klein, D.J.; Bytautas, L. Graphitic Edges and Unpaired π -Electron Spins. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A* **1999**, *103*, 5196-5210, doi:10.1021/jp990510j.
42. Ihnatsenka, S.; Zozoulenko, I.; Kirczenow, G. Band-gap engineering and ballistic transport in edge-corrugated graphene nanoribbons. *Physical Review B* **2009**, *80*, 155415, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.80.155415.

43. Jaskólski, W.; Ayuela, A.; Pelc, M.; Santos, H.; Chico, L. Edge states and flat bands in graphene nanoribbons with arbitrary geometries. *Physical Review B* **2011**, *83*, 235424, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.83.235424.
44. Costa Girão, E.; Cruz-Silva, E.; Liang, L.; Filho, A.G.S.; Meunier, V. Structural and electronic properties of graphitic nanowiggles. *Physical Review B* **2012**, *85*, 235431, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.85.235431.
45. Girão, E.C.; Cruz-Silva, E.; Meunier, V. Electronic transport properties of assembled carbon nanoribbons. *ACS nano* **2012**, *6*, 6483-6491, doi:10.1021/nn302259f.
46. Cuong, N.T.; Otani, M.; Okada, S. Absence of edge states near the 120 corners of zigzag graphene nanoribbons. *Physical Review B* **2013**, *87*, 045424, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.87.045424.
47. Saroka, V.A.; Batrakov, K.G.; Chernozatonskii, L.A. Edge-modified zigzag-shaped graphene nanoribbons: Structure and electronic properties. *Physics of the Solid State* **2014**, *56*, 2135-2145, doi:10.1134/S106378341410028X.
48. Saroka, V.A.; Batrakov, K.G.; Demin, V.A.; Chernozatonskii, L.A. Band gaps in jagged and straight graphene nanoribbons tunable by an external electric field. *Journal of physics. Condensed matter : an Institute of Physics journal* **2015**, *27*, 145305, doi:10.1088/0953-8984/27/14/145305.
49. Saroka, V.A.; Batrakov, K.G. DIRAC ELECTRONS OF GRAPHENE NANORIBBONS TUNABLE BY TRANSVERSE ELECTRIC FIELD. In *Physics, Chemistry and Applications of Nanostructures*, Borisenko, V.E., Gaponenko, S.V., Gurin, V.S., Kam, C.H., Eds.; World Scientific: 2015; pp. 240-243.
50. Szczeńśniak, D.; Durajski, A.P.; Khater, A.; Ghader, D. Energy band gaps in graphene nanoribbons with corners. *EPL (Europhysics Letters)* **2016**, *114*, 48001, doi:10.1209/0295-5075/114/48001.
51. Cao, T.; Zhao, F.; Louie, S.G. Topological Phases in Graphene Nanoribbons: Junction States, Spin Centers, and Quantum Spin Chains. *Physical Review Letters* **2017**, *119*, 076401, doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.119.076401.
52. Lee, Y.-I.; Zhao, F.; Cao, T.; Ihm, J.; Louie, S.G. Topological Phases in Cove-Edged and Chevron Graphene Nanoribbons: Geometric Structures, Z₂ Invariants, and Junction States. *Nano Letters* **2018**, *18*, 7247-7253, doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.8b03416.
53. Ezawa, M. Metallic graphene nanodisks: Electronic and magnetic properties. *Physical Review B* **2007**, *76*, 245415, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.76.245415.
54. Zhang, Z.Z.; Chang, K.; Peeters, F.M. Tuning of energy levels and optical properties of graphene quantum dots. *Physical Review B* **2008**, *77*, 235411, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.77.235411.
55. Kosimov, D.P.; Dzhurakhalov, A.A.; Peeters, F.M. Carbon clusters: From ring structures to nanographene. *Physical Review B* **2010**, *81*, 195414, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.81.195414.
56. Romanovsky, I.; Yannouleas, C.; Landman, U. Unique nature of the lowest Landau level in finite graphene samples with zigzag edges: Dirac electrons with mixed bulk-edge character. *Physical Review B* **2011**, *83*, 045421.
57. Zarenia, M.; Chaves, A.; Farias, G.A.; Peeters, F.M. Energy levels of triangular and hexagonal graphene quantum dots: A comparative study between the tight-binding and Dirac equation approach. *Physical Review B* **2011**, *84*, 245403, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.84.245403.
58. Grujic, M.; Zarenia, M.; Chaves, A.; Tadic, M.; Farias, G.A.; Peeters, F.M. Electronic and optical properties of a circular graphene quantum dot in a magnetic field: Influence of the boundary conditions. *Physical Review B* **2011**, *84*, 205441, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.84.205441.
59. Zarenia, M.; Partoens, B.; Chakraborty, T.; Peeters, F.M. Electron-electron interactions in bilayer graphene quantum dots. *Physical Review B* **2013**, *88*, 245432, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.88.245432.
60. da Costa, D.R.; Zarenia, M.; Chaves, A.; Farias, G.A.; Peeters, F.M. Energy levels of bilayer graphene quantum dots. *Physical Review B* **2015**, *92*, 115437, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.92.115437.

61. Abdelsalam, H.; Espinosa-Ortega, T.; Luk'yanchuk, I. Electronic and magnetic properties of graphite quantum dots. *Low Temperature Physics* **2015**, *41*, 396-400.
62. da Costa, D.R.; Zarenia, M.; Chaves, A.; Farias, G.A.; Peeters, F.M. Magnetic field dependence of energy levels in biased bilayer graphene quantum dots. *Physical Review B* **2016**, *93*, 085401, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.93.085401.
63. Saroka, V.A.; Abdelsalam, H.; Demin, V.A.; Grassano, D.; Kuten, S.A.; Pushkarchuk, A.L.; Pulci, O. Absorption in Finite-Length Chevron-Type Graphene Nanoribbons. *Semiconductors* **2018**, *52*, 1890-1893, doi:10.1134/S1063782618140269.
64. Abdelsalam, H.; Saroka, V.A.; Younis, W.O. Edge functionalization of finite graphene nanoribbon superlattices. *Superlattices and Microstructures* **2019**, *129*, 54-61, doi:10.1016/j.spmi.2019.03.008.
65. Abdelsalam, H.; Atta, M.M.; Saroka, V.A.; Zhang, Q. Anomalous magnetic and transport properties of laterally connected graphene quantum dots. *Journal of Materials Science* **2022**, *57*, 14356-14370, doi:10.1007/s10853-022-07524-x.
66. Stoner, E.C. Collective electron ferromagnetism. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences* **1938**, *165*, 372-414, doi:10.1098/rspa.1938.0066.
67. Stoner, E.C. Collective electron ferromagnetism II. Energy and specific heat. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences* **1939**, *169*, 339-371, doi:10.1098/rspa.1939.0003.
68. Magda, G.Z.; Jin, X.; Hagymási, I.; Vancsó, P.; Osváth, Z.; Nemes-Incze, P.; Hwang, C.; Biró, L.P.; Tapasztó, L. Room-temperature magnetic order on zigzag edges of narrow graphene nanoribbons. *Nature* **2014**, *514*, 608-611, doi:10.1038/nature13831.
69. Ruffieux, P.; Wang, S.; Yang, B.; Sánchez-Sánchez, C.; Liu, J.; Dienel, T.; Talirz, L.; Shinde, P.; Pignedoli, C.A.; Passerone, D.; et al. On-surface synthesis of graphene nanoribbons with zigzag edge topology. *Nature* **2016**, *531*, 489-492, doi:10.1038/nature17151.
70. Wang, S.; Talirz, L.; Pignedoli, C.A.; Feng, X.; Müllen, K.; Fasel, R.; Ruffieux, P. Giant edge state splitting at atomically precise graphene zigzag edges. *Nature Communications* **2016**, *7*, 11507, doi:10.1038/ncomms11507.
71. Lombardi, F.; Lodi, A.; Ma, J.; Liu, J.; Slota, M.; Narita, A.; Myers, W.K.; Müllen, K.; Feng, X.; Bogani, L. Quantum units from the topological engineering of molecular graphenoids. *Science* **2019**, *366*, 1107-1110, doi:10.1126/science.aay7203.
72. Slota, M.; Keerthi, A.; Myers, W.K.; Tretyakov, E.; Baumgarten, M.; Ardavan, A.; Sadeghi, H.; Lambert, C.J.; Narita, A.; Müllen, K.; et al. Publisher Correction: Magnetic edge states and coherent manipulation of graphene nanoribbons. *Nature* **2018**, *561*, E31-E31, doi:10.1038/s41586-018-0297-6.
73. Pavliček, N.; Mistry, A.; Majzik, Z.; Moll, N.; Meyer, G.; Fox, D.J.; Gross, L. Synthesis and characterization of triangulene. *Nature Nanotechnology* **2017**, *12*, 308-311, doi:10.1038/nnano.2016.305.
74. Su, J.; Telychko, M.; Hu, P.; Macam, G.; Mutombo, P.; Zhang, H.; Bao, Y.; Cheng, F.; Huang, Z.-q.; Qiu, Z.; et al. Atomically precise bottom-up synthesis of π -extended [5]triangulene. *Science Advances* **2019**, *5*, 4-10, doi:10.1126/sciadv.aav7717.
75. Mishra, S.; Beyer, D.; Eimre, K.; Ortiz, R.; Fernández-Rossier, J.; Berger, R.; Gröning, O.; Pignedoli, C.A.; Fasel, R.; Feng, X.; et al. Collective All-Carbon Magnetism in Triangulene Dimers**. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2020**, *59*, 12041-12047, doi:10.1002/anie.202002687.
76. Mishra, S.; Xu, K.; Eimre, K.; Komber, H.; Ma, J.; Pignedoli, C.A.; Fasel, R.; Feng, X.; Ruffieux, P. Synthesis and characterization of [7]triangulene. *Nanoscale* **2021**, *13*, 1624-1628, doi:10.1039/D0NR08181G.

77. Su, J.; Fan, W.; Mutombo, P.; Peng, X.; Song, S.; Ondráček, M.; Golub, P.; Brabec, J.; Veis, L.; Telychko, M.; et al. On-Surface Synthesis and Characterization of [7]Triangulene Quantum Ring. *Nano Letters* **2021**, *21*, 861-867, doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.0c04627.
78. Wei, H.; Hou, X.; Xu, T.; Zou, Y.; Li, G.; Wu, S.; Geng, Y.; Wu, J. Solution-Phase Synthesis and Isolation of An Aza-Triangulene and Its Cation in Crystalline Form. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2022**, doi:10.1002/anie.202210386.
79. Wang, T.; Berdonces-Layunta, A.; Friedrich, N.; Vilas-Varela, M.; Calupitan, J.P.; Pascual, J.I.; Peña, D.; Casanova, D.; Corso, M.; De Oteyza, D.G. Aza-Triangulene: On-Surface Synthesis and Electronic and Magnetic Properties. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2022**, *144*, 4522-4529, doi:10.1021/jacs.1c12618.
80. Mishra, S.; Beyer, D.; Eimre, K.; Kezilebieke, S.; Berger, R.; Gröning, O.; Pignedoli, C.A.; Müllen, K.; Liljeroth, P.; Ruffieux, P.; et al. Topological frustration induces unconventional magnetism in a nanographene. *Nature Nanotechnology* **2020**, *15*, 22-28, doi:10.1038/s41565-019-0577-9.
81. Pogodin, S.; Agranat, I. Clar Goblet and Related Non-Kekulé Benzenoid LPAHs. A Theoretical Study. *The Journal of Organic Chemistry* **2003**, *68*, 2720-2727, doi:10.1021/jo026741v.
82. Fernández-Rossier, J.; Palacios, J.J. Magnetism in Graphene Nanoislands. *Physical Review Letters* **2007**, *99*, 177204, doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.99.177204.
83. Wang, W.L.; Yazyev, O.V.; Meng, S.; Kaxiras, E. Topological Frustration in Graphene Nanoflakes: Magnetic Order and Spin Logic Devices. *Physical Review Letters* **2009**, *102*, 157201, doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.102.157201.
84. Güçlü, A.D.; Potasz, P.; Hawrylak, P. Electric-field controlled spin in bilayer triangular graphene quantum dots. *Physical Review B* **2011**, *84*, 035425, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.84.035425.
85. Potasz, P.; Güçlü, A.D.; Hawrylak, P. Zero-energy states in triangular and trapezoidal graphene structures. *Physical Review B* **2010**, *81*, 033403, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.81.033403.
86. Potasz, P.; Güçlü, A.D.; Wójs, A.; Hawrylak, P. Electronic properties of gated triangular graphene quantum dots: Magnetism, correlations, and geometrical effects. *Physical Review B* **2012**, *85*, 075431, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.85.075431.
87. Güçlü, A.D.; Potasz, P.; Hawrylak, P. Zero-energy states of graphene triangular quantum dots in a magnetic field. *Physical Review B* **2013**, *88*, 155429, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.88.155429.
88. Espinosa-Ortega, T.; Luk'yanchuk, I.A.; Rubo, Y.G. Magnetic properties of graphene quantum dots. *Physical Review B* **2013**, *87*, 205434, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.87.205434.
89. Potasz, P.; Güçlü, A.D.; Ozfidan, I.; Hawrylak, P. Spin-orbit coupling and optical detection of spin polarisation in triangular graphene quantum dots. *International Journal of Nanotechnology* **2015**, *12*, 174, doi:10.1504/IJNT.2015.067202.
90. Jaworowski, B.; Potasz, P.; Wójs, A. Disorder induced loss of magnetization in Lieb's graphene quantum dots. *Superlattices and Microstructures* **2013**, *64*, 44-51, doi:10.1016/j.spmi.2013.09.015.
91. Güçlü, A.D.; Potasz, P.; Hawrylak, P. Sublattice engineering and voltage control of magnetism in triangular single and bi-layer graphene quantum dots. *Physica Status Solidi (RRL)* **2016**, *10*, 58-67, doi:10.1002/pssr.201510176.
92. Ge, Y.; Ji, J.; Zhang, Q.; Yuan, Z.; Wang, R.; Zhang, W.; Sang, S. Unraveling the intrinsic magnetic property of triangular zigzag edge bilayer graphene nanoflakes: A first-principles theoretical study. *Chemical Physics Letters* **2019**, *730*, 326-331, doi:10.1016/j.cplett.2019.06.033.
93. Ortiz, R.; Boto, R.A.; García-Martínez, N.; Sancho-García, J.C.; Melle-Franco, M.; Fernández-Rossier, J.n. Exchange Rules for Diradical π -Conjugated Hydrocarbons. *Nano Letters* **2019**, *19*, 5991-5997, doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.9b01773.
94. Ortiz, R.; Fernández-Rossier, J. Probing local moments in nanographenes with electron tunneling spectroscopy. *Progress in Surface Science* **2020**, *95*, 1-16, doi:10.1016/j.progsurf.2020.100595.

95. Gil-Guerrero, S.; Melle-Franco, M.; Peña-Gallego, Á.; Mandado, M. Clar Goblet and Aromaticity Driven Multiradical Nanographenes. *Chemistry – A European Journal* **2020**, *26*, 16138-16143, doi:10.1002/chem.202003713.
96. Jacob, D.; Ortiz, R.; Fernández-Rossier, J. Renormalization of spin excitations and Kondo effect in open-shell nanographenes. *Physical Review B* **2021**, *104*, 075404, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.104.075404.
97. Dong, Y.; Tao, X.; Wang, L.; Wu, Y.; Yu, N.; Bai, L.; Wang, X.; Yang, X.; Liu, Y. Graphene-based nano-devices: high spin Seebeck and pure spin photogalvanic effects. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2021**, *23*, 26476-26481, doi:10.1039/D1CP04214A.
98. Kang, D.; Zhang, S.; Ju, W.; Zuo, Z.-w.; Wang, Z. Heteroatom-doped Clar's goblet: Tunable magnetic order and programmable spin logic gate. *Applied Physics Letters* **2021**, *119*, 192408, doi:10.1063/5.0067405.
99. Bruce, A.V.; Liu, S.; Fry, J.N.; Cheng, H.-P. Clar's Goblet on Graphene: Field-Modulated Charge Transfer in a Hydrocarbon Heterostructure. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2022**, *126*, 5640-5648, doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c00177.
100. Mishra, S.; Beyer, D.; Eimre, K.; Liu, J.; Berger, R.; Gröning, O.; Pignedoli, C.A.; Müllen, K.; Fasel, R.; Feng, X.; et al. Synthesis and Characterization of π -Extended Triangulene. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2019**, *141*, 10621-10625, doi:10.1021/jacs.9b05319.
101. Mishra, S.; Catarina, G.; Wu, F.; Ortiz, R.; Jacob, D.; Eimre, K.; Ma, J.; Pignedoli, C.A.; Feng, X.; Ruffieux, P.; et al. Observation of fractional edge excitations in nanographene spin chains. *Nature* **2021**, *598*, 287-292, doi:10.1038/s41586-021-03842-3.
102. Liu, F.; Wakabayashi, K. Higher-order topology and fractional charge in monolayer graphene. *Physical Review Research* **2021**, *3*, 023121, doi:10.1103/PhysRevResearch.3.023121.
103. Abdelsalam, H.; Abd-Elkader, O.H.; Sakr, M.A.S.; Saroka, V.A.; Zhang, Q. Nanoporous Triangulene-Based Frameworks for the Separation of Petroleum Hydrocarbons: Electronic, Magnetic, Optical, and Adsorption Properties. *ACS Applied Nano Materials* **2023**, doi:10.1021/acsanm.3c02689.
104. Frisch, M.e.; Trucks, G.; Schlegel, H.; Scuseria, G.; Robb, M.; Cheeseman, J.; Scalmani, G.; Barone, V.; Petersson, G.; Nakatsuji, H. Gaussian 16. **2016**.
105. Hehre, W.J.; Ditchfield, R.; Pople, J.A. Self-consistent molecular orbital methods. XII. Further extensions of Gaussian-type basis sets for use in molecular orbital studies of organic molecules. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1972**, *56*, 2257-2261.
106. Becke, A. Density-functional thermochemistry. III. The role of exact exchange (1993) *J. Chem. Phys* **98**, 5648.
107. Lee, C.; Yang, W.; Parr, R.G. Development of the Colle-Salvetti correlation-energy formula into a functional of the electron density. *Physical review B* **1988**, *37*, 785.
108. Abdelsalam, H.; Ali, M.; Teleb, N.H.; Ibrahim, M.M.; Ibrahim, M.A.; Zhang, Q. Two-dimensional Si₂BN nanoflakes for efficient removal of heavy metals. *Chemical Physics Letters* **2021**, *772*, 138568.
109. Abdelsalam, H.; Younis, W.; Saroka, V.; Teleb, N.; Yunoki, S.; Zhang, Q. Interaction of hydrated metals with chemically modified hexagonal boron nitride quantum dots: wastewater treatment and water splitting. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2020**, *22*, 2566-2579.
110. Saad, M.A.; Sakr, M.A.; Saroka, V.A.; Abdelsalam, H. Chemically modified covalent organic frameworks for a healthy and sustainable environment: First-principles study. *Chemosphere* **2022**, *308*, 136581.
111. Grimme, S.; Antony, J.; Ehrlich, S.; Krieg, H. A consistent and accurate ab initio parametrization of density functional dispersion correction (DFT-D) for the 94 elements H-Pu. *The Journal of chemical physics* **2010**, *132*.

112. Lu, T.; Chen, F. Multiwfn: A multifunctional wavefunction analyzer. *Journal of computational chemistry* **2012**, *33*, 580-592.
113. Taylor, J.; Guo, H.; Wang, J. Ab initio modeling of quantum transport properties of molecular electronic devices. *Physical Review B* **2001**, *63*, 245407.
114. Taylor, J.; Guo, H.; Wang, J. Ab initio modeling of open systems: Charge transfer, electron conduction, and molecular switching of a C 60 device. *Physical Review B* **2001**, *63*, 121104.
115. Lieb, E.H. Two theorems on the Hubbard model. *Physical review letters* **1989**, *62*, 1201.
116. Sakr, M.A.; Mohamed, A.A.; Abou Kana, M.T.; Elwahy, A.H.; El-Daly, S.A.; Ebeid, E.-Z.M. Synthesis, characterization, DFT and TD-DFT study of novel bis (5, 6-diphenyl-1, 2, 4-triazines). *Journal of Molecular Structure* **2021**, *1226*, 129345.

Supplementary

Here we show that connecting ZTG by a higher number of even C atoms, e.g. 4C preserves the planer structure of the system. This confirms that the reason for the twisting in the case of 2ZTG-3C is the weaker bonds in the 3C chain not the longer link size compared to 2ZTG-2C. It is also shown in Fig. S1 (g) that a substrate can help solve the twisting problem in the case of odd C-atoms connecting ZTG nanodots.

Fig. S1. (a) The optimized structure of 2ZTG connected with 4C atoms. (b-e) the corresponding HOMO and LUMO for spin-up and spin-down orbitals. (f) The spin density. (g) The optimized structure of 2ZTG-3C situated above the hBN layer, its HOMO, and LUMO are shown in (h-k), and the spin density is in (l).

Fig. S2. The infrared spectra of zigzag-triangular graphene (ZTG) nanodots laterally connected with two and three C atoms.